

Possible Link Between the Correspondence Principle and Extremization of Self-Information?

Francesco R. Ruggeri Hanwell, N.B. April 15, 2019

In classical mechanics, the spatial density for a particle is $1/v(x)$, where $v(x)$ is the velocity which satisfies $.5m v(x)v(x) + V(x) = E$. (Consider an oscillator as an example.) In quantum mechanics, a real wavefunction is defined for a bound state such that spatial density = $W(x)W(x)$ and $W(x)$ satisfies the time-independent Schrodinger equation. As the energy of the Schrodinger equation increases to very levels, it seems that the frequency of oscillations in $W(x)$ and hence of $W(x)W(x)$ increases (e.g. the oscillator). The correspondence principle suggests an envelope function (touching the peaks of these oscillations for levels approaching infinity) will match the classical density $1/v(x)$. In a previous note (1), it was argued one could consider a $Probability(x)Decay Rate(x) = constant$ to demonstrate the correspondence principle. In this note, the idea of self-information, namely $\ln[W(x)W(x)]$, is considered and an extremization equation found. It should be noted, however, that this extremization equation holds only in small neighbourhoods about peak oscillation points of $W(x)$, yet it gives $W(x)W(x)=1/v(x)$ at these points.

Quantum Mechanics

Classical concepts such as $.5 m v(x)v(x)$ already exist in quantum mechanics even for the ground state as $(E-V)W(x)$ in the Schrodinger equation is equal to $.5mv(x)v(x)W(x)$ in all cases. Furthermore, one may write:

$$[(-1/2m) d/dx d/dx W(x)] / W(x) = .5 m v(x)v(x) \quad ((1))$$

This equation holds for all energy levels. Thus, there is a certain curvature even for high energy levels. The Bohr correspondence principle suggests that the envelope function of $W(x)W(x)$ will approach $1/v(x)$ for high energy levels. This does not mean that $W(x)W(x)=1/v(x)$ in the sense of "taking derivatives". When taking derivatives, $W(x)$ must behave as an oscillatory solution of the time-independent Schrodinger equation. It may be the case, however that $W(x \text{ at a peak})W(x \text{ at a peak}) = 1/v(x \text{ at a peak})$ i.e. that the equality holds at isolated points, without generalizations to derivatives of $1/v(x)$.

In (2), the Fourier transform of a quantum oscillator density (hermite polynomial squared times $\exp(-ax^2)$) was taken. Then, a high n limit approximation was performed and the inverse Fourier transform taken to obtain an envelope function equal to $1/v(x)$. This envelope function is not the same as the wavefunction at high energy levels. One cannot take derivatives of the envelope function and expect them to behave in a manner consistent with the time-independent Schrodinger equation. The envelope function and $W(x)W(x)$, however, may touch at peak points of $W(x)W(x)$.

Consider the following relationship at a peak oscillation point:

$$.5m v(x \text{ at peak})v(x \text{ at peak}) = C 1/ W(x \text{ at peak})^4 = (-1/2m) [d/dx d/dx W(x)] / W \quad ((2))$$

The last term in ((2)) is guaranteed to equal $.5m v(x)v(x)$ everywhere, but the second term is not, only at a very high energy peak point of an oscillation.

One can rewrite ((2)) as:

$$1/ (WW) = (-1/2m) W d/dx d/dx W(x) \text{ at } x \text{ peak} \quad ((3))$$

Or:

$$d/d d(x) \ln[d(x)] = (-1/2m) d(x)^{1/2} d/dx d/x d(x)^{1/2} \quad ((4)) \text{ where } d(x)=W(x)W(x)$$

The left hand side of ((4)) looks like a variational result. In general, one would expect a variational result for Shannon's entropy $-d(x) \ln[d(x)]$. Here, one is only interested in a tiny neighbourhood about $x \text{ peak}$ so there is no need to weight the self-information with $d(x)$.

((4)) can be rewritten as:

$$.5m d/d d(x) \ln[d(x)] = (-1/2m) \{ .5 d/dx d/dx d(x) - d(x)^{-1} (d/dx d(x))^2 .25 \} \quad ((5))$$

At the peak point, $d/dx d(x) = 0$. For tiny distances away it seems that the $(d/dx d(x))^2$ would be a tiny value of second order and the other terms may be first order. Thus, it is dropped if this is the case. Then one has:

$$.5m d/d d(x) \ln[d(x)] = (-1/2m) .5 d/dx d/dx d(x) \quad ((6))$$

This is of the form of a variational problem, namely one can extremize:

$$\ln[d(x)] + b [d/dx d(x)]^2 \quad ((7))$$

Here, one uses integration by parts to go from ((7)) to ((6)) and so assumes as in the Lagrangian case that $d(x) + \delta(d(x))$ at the endpoints of the tiny interval is $d(x)$ or $\delta(d(x))=0$ at the endpoints. Otherwise, there would be a term evaluated at both endpoints. The constraint term (with b as a Lagrange multiplier) in ((7)) is of the form of flux velocity.

As a result, it seems that the correspondence principle, applied to peak oscillation points which is where it holds may be related to the extremization of self-information.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we have tried to argue in this note, that one might be able to write the correspondence principle at peak oscillation points of $W(x)$ for very high energy as an extremization problem of the self-information. One does not extremize Shannon's entropy because one is only considering a tiny interval about a peak point. Shannon's entropy could be used if one were consider a region in which density changes. Such an extremization problem seems to be equivalent to matching $W(x)W(x)=1/v(x)$ at a peak point with $.5m v(x)v(x)= (-1/2m) [d/dx d/dx W]$. It seems interesting to try to establish a link with self-information as this emerges naturally in the derivation of the Maxwell-Boltzmann distribution for momentum. In that case, one balances a reaction with its time-reversed case using "and" probability.

$$P(p1)P(p2)=P(p3)P(p4)$$

Taking the natural log of both sides yields a conservation equation in the form of self-information. Matching it to conservation of kinetic energy (for elastic scattering) yields the Maxwell-Boltzmann distribution. In the case considered in this note, self-information seems to appear (although one might argue that it was forced) and it is extremized together with a kinetic energy of flux flow. It is possible the comparison is forced, but it seems interesting that self-information appears both in statistical mechanics and the correspondence principle.

References

1. Ruggeri, Francesco R. The Correspondence Principle and the Idea of Balanced Reactions (preprint, zenodo, 2019)
2. Bernal, J., Martin-Ruiz, Alberto, Garcia-Melgarejo, J. A Simple Mathematical Formulation of the Correspondence Principle 2018 <https://arxiv.org/pdf/1101.1242.pdf>